

Epistemic Insight

TEACHING AND LEARNING ABOUT EPISTEMIC INSIGHT

THE DISCIPLINE WHEEL

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EPISTEMIC INSIGHT AND BIG QUESTIONS

- Can a robot be a good friend?
- How do we keep the planet safe?
- Is artificial life a good thing (does it exist)?
- What do we mean by 'mental health'?
- What is the evidence if any for a multiverse?

www.epistemicinsight.com

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WHAT IS EPISTEMIC INSIGHT?

Epistemic insight refers to 'knowledge about knowledge', and particularly knowledge about disciplines and how they interact.

Research has highlighted that schools typically provide few opportunities for asking multidisciplinary questions and for exploring the distinctive approaches that different disciplines take.

Big Questions are questions like 'Can a robot be a good friend?' and 'Are you really what you eat?'; and 'Why does the universe and everything exist?'. Big Questions bridge science, religion and the wider humanities and they are 'doubly squeezed out' of schools. That's because they don't easily fit into a single subject and rarely if ever have simple agreed answers.

Teaching epistemic insight goes hand in hand with teaching a broad and balanced curriculum. It includes building students' understanding of the ways that different types of disciplinary knowledge can help us to address questions that bridge subjects and disciplines.

Demonstrating epistemic insight – means more than making cross-curricular links. It means you can 'think like a scholar' – you have a sense of curiosity and can plan an investigation. It also means you recognise the strengths and limitations of each of the disciplines.

Which of these questions is a 'good question for science'?
'What do seeds need to grow?' 'Is it always wrong to lie?'

THE EPISTEMIC INSIGHT CURRICULUM FRAMEWORK

The objectives below are from the Epistemic Insight Framework. They are statements about the nature of scholarship and knowledge that reflect the aims of the National Curriculum.

Year Level	Relationships between science and religion	The nature of science in real world contexts and multidisciplinary arenas	Ways of knowing and how they interact
Upper Primary Learning Outcomes	Science and religion are mostly concerned with different types of questions, including different types of why question.	Science begins with observations of the natural world and constructing ways to explain our observations. Some methods are more scientific than others.	Science has some similarities and some differences with other ways of knowing that we learn about in school.
Lower secondary Learning Outcomes	Today we ask big questions about human personhood and the nature of reality that bridge science and religion. Some people say that science and religion are compatible and some people say they are not.	Science informs our thinking about every aspect of our lives. Some questions are more amenable to science than others. There are some questions that science hasn't yet and may never be able to answer.	A school is a multidisciplinary arena. Different disciplines have different preferred questions, methods and norms of thought.
Upper secondary Learning Outcomes	Science and religion are not necessarily incompatible.	Scientism is not a necessary presupposition of science.	Some questions are more metaphysically sensitive than others.

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THE QUESTION BOX

The question in the box has been composed to bridge two disciplines.

Which two disciplines would you choose to help you address this question – and why?

THE 'BUBBLE' TOOL

Some questions are more amenable than others

- Why did the Titanic sink?
- What is the most interesting book ever written?
- Why do things fall to the ground when you let them go?
- Would a robot ever be given the status of a person?
- Why did the Romans come to Britain?
- Will we ever bring back dinosaurs?

THE DISCIPLINE WHEEL

To use the discipline wheel, put a Big Question or topic in the middle such as "what makes us human?". Now choose up to four disciplines and talk about how each one would help you to investigate the question. You can also select two disciplines from opposite sides of the wheel – and compare them.

In this way, you can help your students to appreciate the strengths and limitations of different disciplines. Notice how much is lost if we only use the lens of one discipline to investigate and explain reality.

SAMPLE WORKSHOP

In this activity, students discuss the similarities and differences between a small question that can be answered using science and a big question that doesn't have a simple, agreed answer.

SPAGHETTI

Who will break the spaghetti bridge? Try this fun game that gets students to think about scientific methodology and what kinds of questions are amenable to scientific enquiry.

MATERIALS

- Spaghetti; miniature 'buckets' (made from empty drinks bottles and wire or pipe cleaner, etc.); small stones (mixed weights); and force metres.

HOW TO PLAY

1. Arrange students into groups.
2. Give each group some spaghetti, a 'bucket' and some stones.
3. Ask students to suspend the empty bucket from the spaghetti, which is supported on either end to form a 'bridge'. Decide with the students how many strands of spaghetti to use to make the bridges, and the length of the bridge between the supports
4. Ask students in each group take it in turns to place stones into bucket.
5. The student who places the stone that breaks the spaghetti bridge loses the game. The student who places the last stone before the bucket breaks wins the game.
6. Once all the spaghetti bridges have broken, ask groups measure the weight of the bucket and the stones using the force metres.
7. Collect the data from each of the groups.

DISCUSSION 1

- Ask students to consider what makes the question 'what force is required to break the spaghetti' one that is amenable to science.
- Get the students to think about the methodology of the experiment. Why is it important that each group uses the same number of spaghetti strands and the same length of bridge between the supports? What factors could compromise the results of the experiment?

DISCUSSION 2

- Now ask students to try to explain: 'Who broke the spaghetti and why did the spaghetti break at the moment that it did?'
- Ask students to compare these questions with the previous question. For example, how consistent are the individual groups' answers compared to the answers to the previous question? What different kinds of evidence, or different ways of knowing, are students using to construct their explanations? Do students agree that in this case there isn't a simple answer they can all agree on, but even so our thinking can be informed by many disciplines, including science?

More workshops and resources at www.epistemicinsight.com

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